

PROBLEMS IN LEARNING ENGLISH IN SECONDARY SCHOOL

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Abstract: Knowledge of the English language and proficiency in it, at least at a minimum level, is today the same necessary skill for people as the ability to write and read. Knowledge of languages expands the boundaries of communication and allows you to apply for positions that are much higher paid than positions where a foreign language is not required. Therefore, everyone: parents, children, and teachers select the optimal programs to provide knowledge and level out the difficulties that inevitably arise in the learning process.

Key words: motivation, infancy, tribute, labor-intensive, capability, innate

Introduction

In high school, the main thing for a student is socialization, and not the acquisition of new knowledge and the learning process. Teenagers, as a rule, go to classes to socialize, show themselves, and build new relationships. In these conditions, teachers must provide high-quality material and think through programs that can captivate and fit harmoniously into teenage life.

The article describes four aspects that most often create difficulties in teaching schoolchildren in grades 5-7: the initial level and abilities of students, motivation, program and the ratio of the amount of material and hours allocated to it. The author examines them in detail, offering practical advice based on personal experience.

Knowledge of the English language and proficiency in it, at least at a minimum level, is today the same necessary skill for people as the ability to write and read. Foreign languages within the framework of state school programs begin in the primary grades, and if we talk about upbringing in the family, then, quite likely, from infancy. Yes, this is a tribute to the times - knowledge of languages expands the boundaries

of communication, helps to increase one's social and professional significance, and to apply for positions that are much higher paid than positions where a foreign language is not required. Therefore, everyone: parents, children, and teachers are trying to build a successful system of interaction, select optimal programs to provide knowledge, but not oversaturate it, and level out the difficulties that inevitably arise in the learning process.

Of course, this is a labor-intensive process, in which there are many subtleties and nuances. And if in preschool and primary school age many of the problems can be easily solved with the help of games, then with children in middle school you need to come up with something special.

Adolescence (from 10 to 15 years) is usually characterized as a turning point, even critical. During this period, communication with peers is the dominant type of activity for the child. In communication, moral standards are accepted and learned, characters and rules of behavior are studied, trust and friendship occupy a special place. It is in high school that the main thing for a student is socialization, and not the acquisition of new knowledge and the learning process. Teenagers, as a rule, go to classes to socialize, show themselves, and build new relationships. In addition, for a schoolchild at this age, the approval of "their own" is important, and not the comments and assessment of the teacher. In these conditions, teachers must provide high-quality material and think through programs that can captivate and fit harmoniously into teenage life.

As part of my work, I have identified four aspects that most often create difficulties in teaching schoolchildren in grades 5-7, excluding the features of this age described earlier. I included these: the initial level and abilities of the students, motivation, and, finally, the program and the ratio of the amount of material and the hours allocated to it. Next, we will consider in more detail each problem and possible solutions to them.

The first direction is related to the knowledge and abilities of students. First, let's consider such an aspect as the abilities of schoolchildren. Very often teachers point out this aspect when talking about the difficulties in learning languages. Parents hear phrases: "this child is not able to learn the language," "he has no ability." In order to understand whether these judgments are true, let us turn to theory.

Abilities are a broad concept and the topic of a separate article; in this material we will consider only one of the areas. Human abilities can be divided into general and special. The general ones include brain capabilities associated with memory and intelligence. Special - a narrower group, using the example of the English language, phonemic awareness, imitation skills and innate linguistic competence are considered.

When learning English, both groups are involved: the student remembers foreign words, rules of writing and reading, he analyzes the wording, transfers them to life stories, using the intellect, begins to come up with his own story, remembering and using foreign verbs. And then special skills are involved - hearing and imitation. Students in the class learn to distinguish sounds and then imitate, copy intonations and foreign sounds - and at the next stage they pronounce words, learn to speak and feel the language.

However, a nuance appears: for various reasons, teachers in the classroom do not always have the opportunity to engage all of children's senses, develop their phonetic hearing more deeply, or work hard on imitation. In this regard, it turns out that schoolchildren remember words well and can even come up with a story in English in their heads, but they are afraid or embarrassed to pronounce and start speaking. The learning process is slowed down and then reduced to nothing. At the exit, we hear phrases about the impossibility or inability of the child to master the language.

Most likely, not all of us are given a hundred percent opportunity to master all skills; for some people, they innately develop faster and easier, while others require more effort. At the same time, it is necessary to work with abilities, stimulate them, and also encourage brain cells to work more efficiently.

In my practice, I place a lot of emphasis on listening and watching films in a foreign language. From experience I can say that listening to authentic music. For example, British performers, it helps a lot to involve the guys in the process. Music is a great psychological force and helps the teacher. She relaxes the children, immerses them in the material, we listen to speech patterns, phrases, intonations and pronunciation itself. Under a beautiful and familiar melody, they are better absorbed and remembered, both in sound and meaning. I also use watching movies, for example, at the end of a difficult topic or quarter. Before the holidays. With this type of work, children see facial expressions and gestures, hear the intonation and melody of the language, they can speak along with the characters in the film, without being afraid that they will say something wrong. It is also important that watching films is a kind of remote communication with native speakers. Such materials make it possible to develop linguistic competence, which now a schoolchild may simply sleep or be only partially included in the work of the brain.

Therefore, the students' abilities are not a problem, but an incentive for the teacher to choose more interesting and advanced work formats.

Along with abilities, teachers and I highlight the problem of different levels of knowledge among students in the same class. In most secondary schools, classes include children of different skill levels. In the Big Explanatory Dictionary of the Russian Language, edited by Doctor of Philology S.A. Kuznetsov gives the following definition to the concept of "level": "a stage reached in the development of something; qualitative state, as well as the degree of this development."

According to the generally accepted provisions of methodological science, the level of language proficiency is a certain degree of development of speech skills and

abilities of the user of the language being studied. In a modern school, in one class there may be students who already speak or read English, as well as those who know ten to twenty words. The reasons for the unequal level of knowledge among schoolchildren are completely different: the inability of parents to study (or at least monitor the availability of completed tasks) with children before secondary school and the disinterest of parents in motivating children to learn the language.

For many, the thesis is relevant: school is there to teach, so classes at home and involvement in the process are the task of teachers. This is only partly correct. The task of teaching children, of course, is the responsibility of the teacher, but learning does not end at school; it is a long and varied process. In a good way, after classes the child can consolidate the acquired knowledge and ask what else new could be learned. When at home he meets the interest and keen interest of his parents, the learning is more effective. Low level of knowledge of the teacher in primary school and his inability to transfer knowledge to students.

Next, we will consider a more complex and profound problem in modern schools - the motivation or demotivation of schoolchildren, which often interferes with the educational processes.

Forming motivation to study at school is called one of the central problems of modern schools. Recently, motivation as a concept, its appearance, formation or absence has been studied in more detail, because the life of society has changed dramatically. The future is coming quickly, but for many it is incomprehensible and is associated with the latest technologies, new professions, and digitalization. Of course, this gives rise to various fears in teenagers about their future.

As noted earlier, the teenage or crisis period for schoolchildren is a time of freedom, communication and socialization. Schoolchildren are ready to receive new information and knowledge, but the priority is to master the ways of independently acquiring knowledge, researching what they want, and not what is required.

In addition, parents and society place basic sciences in first place in education: mathematics, Russian language, literature, history. Therefore, according to the residual principle, the English language “comes” when the child is already filled with the required information, dreams of learning what he needs, not the English language, and communicating with the guys on the street. In such situations, schoolchildren do not want to delve into the intricacies and processes of learning a foreign language.

Conclusion

To summarize, I would like to note that ideal programs and educational systems do not yet exist, but all of us: teachers, directors, parents, and children must never tire of looking for opportunities for complete and interesting learning. It is necessary to discuss problems, and then together look for ways to solve them, exchanging experiences, trying, making mistakes, finding new options that will ultimately help provide a quality education to the future generation, strong specialists and successful cities where smart, thoughtful and versatile people work .

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